

CONCEPTS OF EFFECTIVENESS AND EFFICIENCY OF INSPECTION OF AN INCIDENT SITE

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Abstract: The article examines the essence of the organizational and technological components of the practical activities, which are one of the key elements of the forensic system of crime scene investigation, the issues of assessment and control of the traces identified during the inspection of the scene and other material objects relevant to the scene in terms of completeness, timeliness, reliability. Based on the results of the analysis of the scientific views of forensic scientists on the subject, definitions of concepts such as the effectiveness, efficiency and extent of their use in crime detection, as well as the principles of evaluating the effectiveness of forensic technical support were proposed.

Keywords: inspection of the scene of the incident, forensic support, technical forensic and tactical technologies, subjects of forensic support, the effectiveness of the inspection of the scene, the principles of efficiency assessment.

In the case of the discovery of the crime and its effective investigation, the observation of the scene of the incident takes a central place and plays an important role.

It is known that the observation of the scene of the incident is an undue investigative action, consisting in the direct perception and study of objects located in the identified areas of traces and objects that are causally related to the crime under investigation, aimed at identifying, recording and investigating the necessary traces in order to determine the presence and essence of the conditions.

The criminalistic provision of crime scene surveillance is the use by special subjects of knowledge for the purpose of obtaining, collecting, evaluating, processing Criminal Information and using it in the process of further investigation of crimes, it is based on the use of modern technical-criminalistic and tactical-criminalistic tools and technologies in the field of accident surveillance, dynamic organizational-functional system of interrelated

theoretical knowledge and practical components (skills and skills of practical application of organizational, technological and evaluation-control provision).

The objectives of the system under consideration include: the general (final) objective aimed at the detection and investigation of crime as well as the private (intermediate) objectives associated with the objectives of the organizational, technological and evaluation-control parts of the system activities.

The sum of the materialized of the crimeanalytic knowledge (scientific, scientific-practical and educational crimeanalytic literature), together with the system and complexes of technical and crimeanalytic means, constitutes the Bank of the materialized of scientific knowledge, and the science of criminalism presents this knowledge to law enforcement agencies for their application in various areas of combating crime. It is for this reason that the second element of the system of the criminalistic supply of sight of the landing site is this – a practical activity.

It contains the following main components:

1) **organizational (special organizational-criminalistic provision) component (component)** – involvement of a specialist in the examination of the scene of the investigator (interrogator); it is the organizational activity of selecting a specific set of technical-forensic and tactical-forensic tools and technologies required for use in the investigation and their rapid deployment and application at the scene. Organizational aspects of the application of a set of technical means are important in the use of forensic knowledge, as well as the knowledge and skills acquired in the process of forensic education to identify, collect and use information relevant to the detection and investigation of crimes;

2) **technological component (skills and competencies in technical-forensic and tactical-forensic support)**, it consists of the practical application of specialized knowledge, technical-forensic and tactical-forensic tools and technologies by entities that have the knowledge and skills to apply them in crime scene inspections in order to detect, record and obtain evidence.

In our opinion, an effective means of regulating the effectiveness of field inspection consists in the “collection, systematization, analysis and storage of data on the results and effectiveness of the use of technical-criminalistic and tactical-criminalistic tools and technologies”, one of the main components of the quality control system.

For the purposes of the assessment and control component of the practical block (component of the methodological support) of the forensic support system

of the scene, the effectiveness of the use of technical-forensic and tactical-forensic tools in the investigation - the significance of the crime and the incident evaluation and control of other material assets in terms of completeness, timeliness, reliability.

These goals are achieved by solving two-component tasks in the following activities:

first, to assess the effectiveness of the use of technical-forensic and tactical-forensic tools and the effectiveness of forensic support of a specific scene;

secondly, to identify, record, obtain traces of crime and other objects obtained during the inspection of the scene, and to analyze and control the timeliness, reliability and completeness of research.

Qualitative use of technical-forensic and tactical-forensic means during the inspection of the scene allows to solve the tasks provided by the current criminal procedure legislation: gathering defendant's accusatory and acquittal evidence; to identify the circumstances that are important for the proper resolution of the case, to protect the rights and legitimate interests of persons involved in the criminal case, as well as to put forward relevant allegations, examine and choose ways to implement them, and, if necessary, reflect on the nature of the incident;

The Criminal-Procedural Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that "Inquirers, investigators, prosecutors and courts shall evaluate the evidence in accordance with the law and legal consciousness on the basis of careful, complete, comprehensive and impartial consideration of all cases. Each piece of evidence must be evaluated in terms of relevance, acceptability and reliability". Evidence shall be recognized as relevant to the case only if it reflects information about facts or things that confirm, refute or question the conclusions about the existing circumstances that are relevant to the criminal case.

Evidence is considered acceptable only if it is collected in the prescribed manner and meets the conditions provided for in Articles 88, 90, 92-94 of the Criminal-Procedural Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Evidence found to be true as a result of an investigation is considered credible. If all the convincing evidence concerning the case has been collected, which unequivocally confirms the truth of all that has to be proved and each case, their sum is considered sufficient to settle the case.

The assessment of the activities of the subjects of forensic support of the scene inspection on the use of technical-forensic and tactical-forensic means in

conducting this investigative action is not regulated. There are no criteria for such an assessment. Without evaluating these activities, it is impossible to think about the reasonableness of the technical-forensic and tactical-forensic tools and technologies used during the on-site inspection, the effectiveness of their use and the effectiveness of achieving the objectives of the activity in question.

The above indicates the need to develop scientific rules that will allow an objective and timely assessment of the effectiveness of this activity.

Some criminologists (G.I. Gramovich, N.I. Porubov, A.N. Porubov) associate the concept of “efficiency” with the idea of purpose, and “the pre-planned goal was achieved: material evidence was identified, that is, to advance general and specific hypotheses it is necessary to recognize the effectiveness of the search of the scene where the initial information was found, the search for the perpetrators, the stolen items and the victims, the information necessary to identify witnesses”. U.M. Nosirov writes that “... the mobilization of all the knowledge and forces of the investigator, forensic expert, forensic expert, cynologist, operative officer, prevention inspector is important for the effective conduct of the investigation of the scene”. O.D. Kasatonov said, “the effectiveness of the review depends on the tools and methods used by the person conducting it. In this process, a simple (in this case, the only tool is the visual organ) and a qualified (in this case, specially developed tools and methods are used) scans are performed”, but T.B. Mamatkulov, Sh.T. Djumanov, U.T. The Turgunovs write, “The result of an inspection of the scene is a thorough preparation for it”. A.B. Solovyov believes that “the effectiveness of investigative actions means the activity of the investigator, which is optimally organized for their actions, and this activity leads to the achievement of the goals of the investigative actions and their system in general”.

Other authors link effectiveness to the results of efforts made. For example, L.E. Chistova understands efficiency as the objectivity and reliability of obtaining accurate results that correspond to the tasks of criminal proceedings.

V.Ya. According to Karlov, the effectiveness in terms of the use of technical and forensic tools and methods in the investigation of crimes implies the provision of the required result in strict accordance with the requirements of the law. Clearly, the second approach to the concept of ‘effectiveness’ leads to the need to compare it to the concept of “effectiveness”, which is less accurate because G.I. According to Gramovich, the effectiveness (efficiency) of the studied activity is the most important element that determines the level of efficiency.

Therefore, I.I. Yudnikov's view that “the effectiveness of an on-site

inspection means that traces and other material evidence must be obtained during the investigation” can be supported.

N.E. Surygina understands the effectiveness of the technical-forensic support of criminal investigation as the effectiveness of the system. A similar perspective V.A. According to Volynsky, efficiency is the external (environmental) manifestation of the system’s activity, and efficiency is the degree of readiness (adaptability) of the system and its individual elements to solve the tasks assigned to it. However, “provided that the system is not constantly changing, its efficiency may remain unchanged, but its performance may vary”.

A.N. Moskalenko’s opinion that “the effectiveness of the technical and forensic support of the investigation of crimes on” hot leads “is to obtain, process and use as much information as possible to search for the perpetrator in the shortest possible time using forensic techniques and methods”. This view, expressed in terms of efficiency, is an important element in determining the effectiveness of the use of forensic tools in the scene examination. However, in this case it is necessary to think not only about technical, but also tactical-forensic means. Speed means doing the necessary work in the most optimal time, and this is achieved through the rational organization of labor, the use of time-saving tools and methods. “Saving time is the most important indicator of operational efficiency”. V.A. Volynsky’s opinion that “it is wrong to evaluate efficiency only by the result, because often the result depends on the external conditions in which the system must work” is also correct.

It is also interesting to note that a number of criminologists believe that “efficiency is the degree to which goals are achieved when the level of efficiency is determined by the ratio of goals and results achieved”. It is proposed to determine such a ratio on many indicators (not only statistical averages), using all possible sources of information and methods of obtaining, analyzing and evaluating information.

As noted above, the ultimate goal of forensic crime scene investigation is to effectively obtain, collect, evaluate, and process information of forensic significance for use in future criminal investigations as a result of an investigative action.

In conclusion, it should be noted that:

It is recommended to understand the effectiveness of forensic support of the scene investigation - the degree to which its results are achieved in practice, expressed in key elements such as the effectiveness and degree of use in the

rapid investigation of the crime.

The level of efficiency is determined by the ratio of the result obtained and the goal set.

The effectiveness of the criminalistic provision of the scene of the accident survey – indicates that it is necessary to provide for the purpose of identifying, recording and obtaining traces of crime and other objects in the use of technical-criminalistic and tactical-criminalistic means of Investigation, as well as information of preliminary (directing) criminalistic significance, their operational research.

The level of use of the results obtained in the investigation of the scene in the investigation of crimes reflects the contribution of forensic information obtained as a result of the use of technical-forensic and tactical-forensic tools in the investigation of crimes, including “hot pursuit”.

N.E. as a principle of evaluating the effectiveness of technical-forensic support of scene investigation. The principles proposed by Surygina can be considered:

- 1) taking into account the final results of the criminal investigation;
- 2) adequacy (consistency of assessment criteria with the goals and objectives to be addressed in the use of technical and forensic knowledge and the level of organization of this activity);
- 3) objectivity;
- 4) completeness and comprehensiveness of the assessment, arising from the accounting and analysis of all forms of technical and forensic knowledge in different forms, the application of different forms by different entities;
- 5) clarity of assessment;
- 6) timeliness of assessment.

In order to think about the effectiveness of forensic examination of the scene, it is necessary to select certain criteria for evaluating this activity.

Criterion is a sign that is the basis of the assessment of the studied event, action, feature, property, state, that is, on the basis of the sign, the studied event, action, feature, property, state, etc. are evaluated. “Criterion is a measure, a standard for comparison or evaluation”.

The diversity of the tasks of forensic support of the scene, the use of technical-forensic and tactical-forensic means in the conduct of this investigation, as well as the diversity of work performed under these conditions implies the existence of a system of criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of such supply.

In developing such a system of criteria, it is important to identify the specific requirements that their selection must meet.

The criteria must meet the following requirements:

- compliance with the tasks and functions of the body and person whose activities are being evaluated;
 - comparable, agreed and non-contradictory;
 - easy to use;
 - help to achieve the goal;
- sufficiently describe the activity in quantitative and qualitative terms, allow for an objective, complete and comprehensive assessment of efficiency.

References:

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Жиноят-протсессуал кодекси. – Т., 2019;
2. Н.И. Порубов. Криминалистика: учеб. пособие / Н.И. Порубов, Г.И. Грамович, А.Н. Порубов; под ред. Н.И. Порубова. – Минск, 2007;
3. Носиров У.М. Ҳодиса жойини кўздан кечириш: Ўқув-амалий кўлланма. - Т: Ўзбекистон Республикаси ИИВ Академияси, 2014;
4. О.Д. Касатонов Криминалистическое исследование. – Киев, 2000;
5. Криминалистик тактика: Дарслик / Т.Б.Маматкулов, Ш.Т.Джуманов, У.Т.Тургунов ва бошқ. - Т.: Ўзбекистон Республикаси ИИВ Академияси, 2013;
6. А.Б. Соловев. Проблемы эффективности следственных действий: автореф. дис. ... д-ра юрид. наук: 12.00.09 / Всесоюз. ин-т по изучению причин и разраб. мер предупреждения преступности. - М., 1985;
7. Л.Е. Чистова. Техничко-криминалистическое обеспечение осмотра места происшествия: учеб. пособие / Моск. юрид. ин-т. - М., 1998;
8. В.Г. Кутушев. Методологические проблемы отсенки эффективности деятельности следственных органов / Проблемы предварительного следствия и раскрытия преступлений в деятельности органов внутренних дел: сб. науч. тр. / Хабар. высш. шк; редкол: В.Г. Кутушев (отв. ред.) [и др.]. - Хабаровск, 1989;
9. Р.К. Абдуллаев. Ҳодиса жойини кўздан кечиришнинг криминалистик таъминоти мақсад ва вазифалари // Юридик фанлар ахборотномаси, ТДЮУ. Ҳуқуқий илмий-амалий журнал. 2021/2.
<https://tadqiqot.uz/index.php/law/article/view/3529>;
10. Абдуллаев, Р. 2023. Ҳодиса жойини кўздан кечиришнинг криминалистик технологияси тушунчаси. Общество и инновации. № 10 (2021).
<https://inscience.uz/index.php/socinov/article/view/1389>;

11. Abdullaev Rustam Kahramanovich, (2023). Questions of conducting an expert experiment. The American Journal of Political Science Law and Criminology, 5(11). <https://doi.org/10.37547/tajpslc/Volume05Issue11-04>;
12. Абдуллаев, Р. 2023. Вопросы проведения экспертного эксперимента. Общество и инновации. 4, 9/S (ноя. 2023).
DOI:<https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-1415-vol4-iss9/S-pp82-88>;
13. Абдуллаев, Р. 2023. Преобразование сведений по делу в виде заключения эксперта. Общество и инновации. 4, 3/S (май 2023).
<https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-1415-vol4-iss3/S-pp48-56>;
14. Abdullaev Rustam Kahramanovich . (2022). Inspection of the scene of the incident using advanced technologies. The American Journal of Political Science Law and Criminology, 4(10).
<https://doi.org/10.37547/tajpslc/Volume04Issue10-09>;
15. Abdullaev, R. (2023). Jinoyatlarni tergov qilishda zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalanish. Theoretical Aspects in the Formation of Pedagogical Sciences, 2(9).
<http://www.econferences.ru/index.php/tafps/article/view/5983>;
16. Абдуллаев, Р. 2023. Суд экспертиза тадқиқоти услублари тизимида экспериментнинг ўрни. Юрист ахборотномаси. 5, 3 (2023).
<https://yuristjournal.uz/index.php/lawyer-herald/article/view/895>.

